

Mediterranean challenges for
food safety and authenticity of
**SMALL RUMINANT
MILK CHEESES**

Handbook

Mediterranean challenges for food safety and authenticity of small ruminant milk cheeses

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Preamble

This Handbook is a one of products of the EU PRIMA MEDIFIT project, funded by the Horizon 2020 - PRIMA joint program, which is focused on the development and application of solutions for food systems and water resources in the Mediterranean basin. The EU PRIMA MEDIFIT project focuses on the valorization of two Mediterranean products, honey and cheese. In order to improve marketing and strengthen the quality and image of these products as well as consumer confidence, MEDIFIT has the general objective of enabling the traceability and control of the authenticity of traditional Mediterranean foods using the latest technologies, analytics and software (Figure 1). The MEDIFIT consortium, involving 6 Mediterranean countries and 12 socio-economic partners, has the mission to develop a flexible, modular and standards-based software framework that provides end users with the necessary communication interfaces and web software solutions and facilitates the use of innovative analytical methods to assess the traceability and integrity of foods and confirm the authenticity of goat's and sheep's honey and cheeses.

Figure 1. Overall concept of MEDIFIT Project.

Food fraud, including the more defined subcategory of economically motivated adulteration, is a public-health food risk that is growing in awareness, concern, and danger. Each food fraud incident has the potential to threaten consumers’ well-being but also undermine confidence in the EU food market. The impact may be higher for the Mediterranean traditional food products considering that they are generally recognized for their high nutritional and sensory value. The recent example of the honey fraud between China and US of relabelled filtered honey (free of pollen) to remove traces of its origins is a characteristic example of a traceability flaw. Milk and honey are among the top 6 products that are more at risk of food fraud , while in the monthly Food Fraud summary of the EU honey and milk products (cheese) are the most frequently reported foods. For example, foreign sugars were found 1.4 times in every 10 honey samples tested by the European Joint Research Centre, according to research published in December 20162 . Other common adulterations of honey with potential safety, or economic impact include: artificial coloring, unjustified organic labels and fake geographical and botanical origin. In the case of cheese, apart from the geographical origin, the use of bovine milk instead of ovine and microbial contaminations are common problems.

The overarching objective of MEDIFIT is to enable traceability, authenticity control of traditional Mediterranean foods integrating innovative analytical methods and digital technologies. To accomplish that, the consortium will link Decision Support Systems (DSSs) to a cloud-based Distributed Data and Service Integration BackBone (DDSIBB) providing access to decentralized food integrity information repositories. MEDIFIT will implement this IT-standards-driven solution for food integrity scenarios in two Mediterranean food chains: honey and cheese products by adopting a multi-actor approach from farm to fork.

Introduction

Sheep and goat's milk cheeses have a long and captivating history, originating from ancient civilizations in the Mediterranean region. These civilizations greatly esteemed sheep and goats for their ability to produce milk and cheese. In fact, cheese production served as a practical method for preserving milk prior to the invention of refrigeration.

Throughout the course of history, cheese has played a fundamental role in the diets and cultures of various Mediterranean societies. It was highly prized for its adaptability, nutritional advantages, and distinct flavor. The process of creating cheese involves curdling milk through the use of acids or enzymes, resulting in the separation of solid curds from liquid whey. The outcome is a delectable, handcrafted small ruminant milk cheese with a smooth consistency and a diverse range of textures and flavors, ranging from mild and buttery to tangy and sour. The production process demands expertise and skill to ensure that each batch of small ruminant milk cheese attains the utmost quality.

Small ruminant milk cheeses are well-known for their nutritional value, distinctive sensory qualities, and ability to enhance the flavor of dishes. Both are an excellent source of protein, calcium, phosphorus, vitamins A and B12, and omega-3 fatty acids. Sheep's milk is typically higher in solids, fat, protein, and casein, but it also contains more minerals and vitamins than other species' milk. Goat milk composition in small-chain fatty acids makes it often easier to digest than cow's milk cheese. Small ruminant cheeses also contain various proteins that may be more tolerable to individuals allergic to cow's milk and may also be suitable for those with lactose intolerance. The taste of these cheeses can vary depending on factors such as the breed of sheep or goat, their diet, and the maturation process. Typically, sheep cheese has a nutty flavor with a subtle hint of grassiness, which adds depth and complexity to its taste. Goat milk cheese has a particular “goaty” and “barnyardy” flavor, related to a higher amount of three smaller-chain fatty acids (caproic, capric and caprylic acids).

The increasing prevalence of globalization, urbanization, and consumer awareness of the necessity of healthy, sustainable food has led to a growing demand for small ruminant dairy products in particular. Additionally, this dairy sector contributes to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations' agenda 2030 (United Nations, 2015), particularly regarding SDG 2: Eradicate hunger, Ensure food security, Improve nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture, SDG3: Enable all people to live in good health and promote well-being for all at all ages, SDG5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls, SDG8: Promote sustained, shared and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all, SDG12: Establish sustainable consumption and production patterns, and SDG15: Conserve and restore terrestrial ecosystems, ensuring their sustainable use, Manage forests sustainably, Combat desertification, Halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.

Despite the positive reputation of dairy products (from a societal perspective) and the general acknowledgement of the importance of various small ruminant farming systems in environmental

conservation (including the conservation of animal diversity and genetics) and the economic development of rural areas, the sustainability of the small ruminant dairy industry in the Mediterranean region is currently being questioned. This is primarily due to the effects of multiple factors, including strong pressure on food resources (pasture, rangelands), increasing feed costs, the dangers of climate change, as well as the lack of skilled labor associated with the aging of breeders and the rural exodus. The volume of herds, the troubles with management, the collective's limitations, as well as the small-scale production and marketing issues, can all be detrimental to the sector's sustainability.

The present handbook aimed at tackling Mediterranean challenges in the small ruminant milk cheese sub-sector on one hand, and on the other hand, at promoting the MEDIFIT digital solution for a better food safety and traceability, by identifying novel policy strategies, policy instruments, governance mechanisms and institutional changes required to foster transitions towards a new paradigm of digital food companies in a longer term perspective.

Current situation of the small ruminant dairy sector

The dairy industry is one of the primary components of the agricultural system around the world. The FAO estimates that it has a contribution of 27% to the global total of livestock value, and 10% to agriculture (FAO, 2016). Other than its financial importance, it's also of significant interest from a nutritional perspective, due to the wide variety of dairy products intended for human consumption.

1.1 Dairy production

According to the FAO, global milk production has increased by more than 59% over the last three decades, from 530 million tons in 1988 to 843 million tons (Mt) in 2018. The OECD/FAO (2023) forecasts an increase of 1.5% per year over the next ten years to reach 1,039 Mt in 2032: this increase would be faster than that of most major agricultural products. In 2022, India will be the world's largest milk producer, accounting for 22% of world production, followed by the United States, China, Pakistan and Brazil (OECD/FAO, 2023). According to OECD/FAO (2023), over the next ten years, approximately 30% of global milk production will be used for processing into butter, cheese, whole or skimmed milk powder, or whey powder. In fact, the consumption of dairy products, including cheese, has increased worldwide due to the increasing trend of westernization of food consumption patterns, economic growth, the rise of the middle class and increasing urbanization. In the Middle East/North Africa (NENA) region, per capita availability of dairy products is expected to increase from 10.8 kg per capita per year (2019-2021) to 11.4 kg per year in 2032 (OECD/FAO 2023).

1.1.1 Milk production

Global milk production consists of approximately 83% cow's milk, 14% buffalo milk, 2% goat and camel milk, and 1% sheep milk (Table 1: FAO, 2016).

Table 1 : World milk production by dairy animal species (FAO, 2016)

Animal	Quantities (Tons)	Pourcentage
Cow	675 621 019	82
Bufflonne	120 353 705	14
Goat	18 656 727	2
Sheep	10 400 639	1
Camel	2 852 213	0,3
Total	827 884 303	100

The domestic sheep (*Ovis aries*) is a very widespread small ruminant species raised primarily for its wool, meat, milk, and skins, according to FAO. The species has evolved into a variety of breeds adapted for different purposes in different environments. These range from the cold, wet highlands of northern Europe to the arid regions of Africa, Asia and Australasia. Sheep are primarily grazers, grazing close to the ground. They are reared in a wide variety of production systems around the world, reflecting prevailing environmental conditions and socio-economic contexts, according to the FAO. World production of fresh ewe's milk was estimated by the FAO at 10.56 Mt in 2020. It increased by 11.74% between 2010 and 2020 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Global trends in sheep milk production between 2010 and 2020 (expressed in million tons) (Tridge, 2022)

Figure 3: Global geographical distribution of sheep's milk production (FAO, 2016)

The two main producers of sheep's milk in 2020 were China (14.7%) and Turkey (14.6%), followed by the European Mediterranean countries: Greece (11.5%), Italy (5.8%) and Spain (6.7%) according to Tridge (2023). In Spain, sheep production has increased from 368 t in 2011 to 588 t in 2020, whereas in Turkey it reached 1 521 000 tons in 2019. The African continent produces approximately a quarter of the international stock of sheep's milk, with subsistence production systems in countries such as Syria (8.5%), Algeria (7.2%), Sudan (5%) and Somalia (4.9%). In Tunisia, milk from non-bovine species (small ruminants and camels) accounts for only 3.7% of total national production, and its industrial processing remains fairly low (Chniter et al. 2021; OEP, 2022). The sheep flock comprises 6.47 million heads (rams, ewes, lambs and antenais-antenaisses) distributed mainly in the North and Centre regions (INS, 2020). In Tunisia, dairy sheep are mainly Sicilian-Sardinian, the only specialized dairy breed in North Africa. It is the result of crossbreeding of Comisane and Sarde, two Italian breeds from Sicily and Sardinia respectively, renowned for their exceptional performance in the Mediterranean basin. It was introduced at the beginning of the 20th century, by Italian migrant breeders established in northern Tunisia, introducing a tradition of consuming ewe's milk cheese in the region (Aloulou et al., 2018). The domestic goat (*Capra aegagrus hircus*) is a species that is commonly found in small rural communities, reared primarily for meat, milk, hide and hair, according to the FAO. Unlike the cattle and sheep species, goats are primarily grazers that have a diverse diet of herbs, which has allowed them to adapt to different habitats. Their production is performed worldwide through multiple different systems. The majority of the animals are raised in smallholder farming systems that are mixed with grazing, but goats have a significant role in the dairy industry and are important animals that are specialized in the production of high value products in temperate regions. The worldwide dairy goat population was evaluated to be 218 million in 2017. Dairy goat numbers have experienced consistent growth globally, with significant spikes in the 1990s (Figure 4). In 2017, Asia had the highest percentage of the global population at 52%, followed by Africa (39%), Europe (5%), the Americas (4%), and Oceania (<1%). Interestingly, due to increasing specialization and commercialization, Europe supplies 15% of goat milk with only 5% of the population. In Turkey, goat milk production has increased from about 320 000 t in 2011 to 577 000 t in 2019. According to FAO, goat's milk is more consumed than cow's milk worldwide (Miller & Lu, 2019).

Figure 4: World dairy goat population (heads) during 1961 to 2017 (from Miller & Lu, 2019).

1.1.2 Cheese production

The global demand for all dairy products is expected to rise further as consumers become more affluent and consume more animal products. According to Statista (October 2023), over 549 million metric tons of cow's milk were produced worldwide in 2023, among other dairy products. In comparison, the volume of cheese and butter produced in the same year was over 22 and 11 million metric tons, respectively. In fact, cheese is the most consumed dairy product in terms of solids worldwide. Global cheese production has increased in recent years (Statista, 2023). Moreover 22.17 million tons of cheese were produced worldwide in 2022, with the European Union (EU) leading the way with a production volume of roughly 10.55 million tons of cheese (Statista, 2023).

Table 2: Rank of the world's major cheese producers (Statista, 2023)

Rank	Country	NATIONAL PRODUCTION 1000 metric tons
1	USA	6 217
2	Germany	2 361
3	FRANCE	1 856
4	ITALY	1 374
5	RUSSIA	1 075
6	NETHERLANDS	954
7	POLAND	920
8	BRAZIL	790
9	TURKEY	755
10	SPAIN	548

Cow's milk cheese accounts for 94% of global production, following cheeses from sheep's milk (3%), goat's milk (2%), and buffalo milk (1%)(FAO, 2016). In the EU (European Parliament 2017), only 3% of milk came from non-cow animals, such as ewes, goats, and buffalo (Figure 5). Dairies received the majority of the milk produced (71% for sheep and goat milks).

Figure 5. Production and use of milk in the EU (in million tons)(European Parliament 2017)

In the EU (European Parliament 2017), only five nations provided nearly all of the milk from sheep and goats (92%): Greece (24%), Spain (23%) France (19%), Romania (14%) and Italy (12%). Whether it is produced on a farm or in commercial dairies, almost all of the milk is utilized to make cheese. In 2015, 9 % of total EU cheese production was from ewe's, goat's or mixed milk (about 850 000 tons)(European Parliament, 2017).

Sheep's milk cheese refers to a variety of fresh, hard, and soft sheep's milk cheeses. Sheep's milk cheese contains more fat than cow's or goat's milk cheese, making it richer and creamier than other forms of cheese. It also has a distinct flavor profile that includes notes of almonds, grass, and herbs. It's also popular for its digestibility and nutritional worth. Greece is the world's largest producer of sheep's milk cheese, followed by China and Spain.

Figure 6. World’s Main Sheep Cheese Country Producers (FAO, 2016).

Goat cheese refers to cheeses with various flavors and textures - from creamy to crumbly, young to mature, mild to earthy and tangy. Europe is the world's leading producer of goat cheese (Table 3; FAO, 2019).

Table 3: Rank of the world's major goat cheese producers (FAO, 2019)

Rank	Country	NATIONAL PRODUCTION metric tons
1	Soudan	114 820
2	France	100 680
3	Spain	48 350
4	Niger	40 755
5	Greece	40 570
6	Iran	37 109
7	Mexico	16 764
8	Tajikistan	14 452
9	Afghanistan	10 386
10	China	6 644

Turkey has produced 236 tons of goat cheese in 2021. Actually, the cheese sector is moving toward the new standard of sustainability. Throughout the production process, cheese makers and manufacturers are implementing environmentally friendly methods, such as obtaining milk from nearby organic farms and cutting carbon emissions.

1.1.3 Quality of small ruminant milks and dairy products

Small ruminant milks have an interesting nutrient profile, when compared to cow milk. As shown in Table 4, sheep's milk contains higher levels of fat, proteins (particularly caseins), and minerals compared to goat and bovine milk. In contrast to cow's milk (Balthazar et al., 2017), sheep and goat milks have lower levels of alpha S1 caseins associated with allergic reactions. Moreover, sheep's milk has higher levels of serine, alanine, histidine, valine, and lysine, along with lower levels of cysteine and glycine than cow's milk (Table 4). Goat and sheep milk contain more calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, and iron, along with fat-soluble vitamins such as vitamins A, and D, than cow milk (Nguyen, 2022). For decades, goat milk has been considered a nutraceutical due to its simple digestion when compared to bovine milk (Clark and Mora Garca, 2017).

Table 4 : Average Milk Composition from different animals (Balthazar et al., 2017 ; Mohapatra et al., 2019 ; Nguyen, 2022)

Nutriments	Sheep	Goat	Cow
Fat (%)	7,9	3,8	3,6
Non solid fat (%)	12,0	8,9	9,0
Lactose (%)	4,9	4,1	4,7
Proteins (%)	6,2	3,4	3,2
Caseins (%)	4,2	2,4	2,6
Ashes (%)	0,9	0,8	0,7
Calcium	0.13	0.19	0.12
Vitamin A (mg/100mL)	0.07	0.05	0.04
Vitamin D (microg/100mL)	0.16	0.25	0.09
Vitamin E (mg/100mL)	0.20	0.10	0.12
Calories/ml	105	70	69

The fundamental feature of small ruminant milk fat is their high level of short- and medium-chain fatty acids (MCFA), particularly in goat milk fat, which contains at least twice as much C6-C10 fatty acids as cow milk fat: 8%, 12%, and 16% total fatty acid for cow, ewe, and goat milk fat, respectively. These fatty acids contribute to the characteristic aromatic note of cheeses (Balthazar et al., 2017; Mohapatra et al., 2019). The fraction of monounsaturated fatty acids represents on average 24 g/100 g of total fatty acids (mainly oleic acid). Sheep's milk has a higher content of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), on average 4.5 g/100 g, than cow's and goat's milk (4.05 and 3.70% respectively). In addition, the proportion of conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) in sheep's milk is higher than cow's milk (1.08 and 0.65% respectively). The ratio between n-6 PUFA and n-3 PUFA is lower in sheep's milk than in goat's and cow's milk (respectively 2.3, 5.0 and 6.0), making it interesting on the nutritional plan in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases. These properties of raw milk's lipidic fraction are crucial for its products, particularly cheese, as long as cheese processing does not lead to significant changes. The globule size of small ruminant milk fat is another distinguishing feature. Some research on this topic has demonstrated that small ruminant milks have a higher proportion of small globules than cow milk (Nguyen, 2022). Consequently small ruminant milk is easier to digest due to the presence of these small fat globules scattered throughout it (Nguyen, 2022). Some research has found a link between caprine s1 casein genotype and fat globule size (Nguyen, 2022). Balthazar et al. (2017) reported that sheep's milk casein micelles have higher degrees of mineralization and are less hydrated and more heat stable than cow's milk casein micelles.

Calcium contributes to the coagulation of rennet, inducing cross-linking and aggregation of paracasein. Furthermore, casein micelles from sheep's milk are richer in calcium than those from cow's milk, and no CaCl₂ additive is necessary for the production of sheep's cheese, which constitutes a technological advantage (Pazzola, 2019). Additionally, producing satisfactory curd from sheep's milk requires less rennet or chymosin than cow's or goat's milk (Balthazar et al., 2017; Pazzola, 2019). More specifically for Tunisian sicilo sarde sheep's milk, Bousselmi and Othmane (2015) established the average cheese yield for a white cheese at 33.87 ± 6.10 Kg/100 L.

The market for sheep and goat milk and their products is expanding as demand for conventional cheese and dairy products rises (Industry ARC, 2022). Main cheeses made from goat and sheep milks are : Feta, Roquefort, Pecorino Romano, Manchego, Chèvre, Cabrales, Valdeón, Halloumi, Bucheron, Garrotxa, Zamorano, Serra da Estrela, Crottin de Chavignol, Ragusano, Sardinian Pecorino, Pyrenees Brebis, Pouligny-Saint-Pierre, Malvarosa, Selles-sur-Cher, Ossau-Iraty, Rigoutta (North Africa).

Sheep's milk cheese contains twice as much fat as cow's or goat's milk cheese, as well as more minerals, vitamin C, vitamin B12, folic acid, calcium, and magnesium (Balthazar et al., 2017). Raynal-Ljutovac et al. (2008) have reviewed the composition of sheep milk cheeses from different breeds and aging (Table 5).

Table 5. Gross composition of some sheep milk cheeses (%; from Raynal-Ljutovac et al. 2008; MEDIFIT-INAT)

Product/cheese	Breed	Age of cheese	Total solids	Fat	Proteins	Ash
Ricotta	Sarda		30	18		
Canestrato pugliese		1-56 days	39	31	25	
Canestrato pugliese		10-12 months	67	30	27	
Flore sarde			70	29	28	
Pecorino romano			65	30	27	
Manchego		90 days	63			
Soft Lactic	Sicilo sarde	0-33 days	53	26		
Manchego	Manchega	1-9 months	37	31	25	
Feta		3-240 days	45	22	18	
Serra da estrela		1,7,21,35 days				8
Manchego			66			7
Serena			58			9
Halloumi		Fresh	65	32	23	
Terrincho		0-60 days	46	25	21	8
Pecorino	Sarda	1/60 days	70	37/36	26	
Manchego	Manchega	90 days	70	30/42/37	23	
Los Pedroches	Merinos	2-100 days	35	31/33	26	8
Robiola della Langhe		1,11,28 days	49	24	18	5
Roquefort			57	33	19	6
Ossau-Iraty			61	32	24	4
Rigoutta of Béja	Sicilo sarde	Fresh	27	59	31	4.5
Affiné of Béja	Sicilo sarde		67	30	32	2.5
Sicilien of Béja	Sicilo sarde		45	22	23	2

The cheese processing has little to no effect on the FA profile of different sheep milk cheeses (Moatsou & Sakkas, 2019). FA analysis of commercial sheep milk cheeses have revealed the highest amounts of unsaturated and polyunsaturated FA, CLA, and n-3 FA when compared to buffalo, cow, and goat milk cheese (n=133 samples; Manuelian et al., 2017). When compared to cow cheeses, sheep and goat milk cheeses were higher in SCFA (Paszczyk & Łuczyska, 2020). In addition, Manuelian et al. (2017) indicated no difference in the cholesterol content of different commercial cheeses based on the type of milk used; sheep and cow milk cheeses both had about 0.07 grams of cholesterol per 100 grams of cheese. The high fat content gives it a creamy texture (Pazzola, 2019). Sheep's milk cheese has a distinct flavor that is clean, sweet, and slightly grassy. It is also less difficult to digest.

Sheep's cheeses have distinct sensory characteristics due to the diversity of the microbial flora in raw milk. It also contains probiotic lactic acid bacteria, specifically the health-promoting *Enterococcus*. Goat cheese has an interesting nutritional value, mainly related to its low content in fat and cholesterol. Table 6 indicated the composition of some goat milk cheeses from different countries, reviewed by Raynal-Ljutovac et al. (2008).

Table 6. Gross composition of some goat milk cheeses (%; from Raynal-Ljutovac et al. 2008)

Product	Type of cheese/age for analysis	Study country	Total solids	Fat	Proteins	Lactose	Ash	Salt
Manchego type	Fresh	Spain	59	34	22		4	1.5
	Semi mature		65	36	23		5	2.2
	Long ripening		71	35	25		4	1.9
Cheddar type		USA	58	27	30	1.4		
Cheddar type	Hard, 6 months	USA	62	28	22			
Colby type	Washed curd, 6 months	USA	54	21	18			
Soft lactic		USA	34	16	13			
Domiat	Egyptian soft cheese, fresh	USA	38	15	12			
Cacioricotta	Soft, 7 days	Italy	47	17	17			3.0
Apulian	Fresh soft	Italy	36	17	14	2.3	1.7	0.3
Cacioricotta	rennet cheese							
Ricotta	Whey cheese, 1 day	Italy	31	21	7	2.9	0.9	
Servilletta	Slightly pressed	Spain	38	18	14			
Brocciu	Sweet whey cheese	France	29	17	6			
	Mixed whey cheese		25	13	6			
Babia Iaciana		Spain	71					
Vadeja	27 days	Spain	73	43	26		4.5	2.1
Armada	Pressed rennet type cheese, 120 days	Spain	79	57	37		3.0	1.7
Feta type	21 days	S. Africa	41	17	15			4.1
Rocamadour	Soft lactic	France	41	2				1.7
Ste Maure	Soft lactic, 21 days	France	49	27	12			
	Soft lactic, 58 days		66	36	16			
Valencay	Soft lactic	France	40	20	16	1.8		
Crottin de Chavignol	Soft lactic	France	41	23	0.7	0.7		
Fresh cheese	15 days	Spain	44	22	16		2.7	0.8
Majoreto	90 days	Spain	61	32	22		4.5	2.8
Bastelicaccia	Soft, ripened, 30 days	France	60	33				2.1
Cendrat Montsec	Mixed coagulation, 63 days	Spain	51	31	18		2.2.	

Goat milk cheese has a rich nutrient profile including vitamins A, B1, B2, and B3, calcium, phosphorus, and proteins (Raynal-Ljutovac et al., 2008; Tafes, 2020). Compared to bovine cheese, it has less calories, fat, and cholesterol. According to Paszczyk & Łuczyńska (2020), goat cheeses had the lowest values of the thrombogenicity index (TI) (2.67 ± 0.44) and a higher amount of n-3 polyunsaturated fats (PUFAs), in comparison to sheep and cow cheeses (3.14 ± 0.29 and 3.13 ± 0.13 , respectively). Further, goat cheese is easier on the digestive system (Tafes, 2020). This in turn drives the consumption of goat cheese as health-conscious consumers are increasingly food products that help to improve digestive health (Mordor Intelligence, 2022).

The diversity of the microbial flora of raw milk gives sheep and goat cheeses particular sensory characteristics. They also contain probiotic lactic acid bacteria. The quality of sheep's cheese is related to that of the raw material. Indeed, Balthazar et al. (2017) reported the main factors affecting cheese yield, namely somatic cell levels, microbial load, genetic and physiological factors. Moreover, organoleptic quality of these cheeses have a significant impact on their marketability and acceptability among consumers (Tafes, 2020).

1.2 Consumption

According to the OECD/FAO (2023), cheese consumption has increased worldwide. The highest was observed in The European Union (EU), with an average cheese consumption of 20.96 kg per capita in 2022 (Figure 7; Statista, 2023). France, a nation well-known for its cheese culture, had a per capita consumption of 26.8 kg in 2019, which was much higher than the EU average. In Spain per capita cheese consumption has increased from 2.82 Kg in 2011 to 3.92 Kg in 2020.

The United States and Canada ranked second and third, respectively, with 17.8 and 14.85 kg of cheese consumed per capita (Statista, 2023).

Figure 7: Per capita consumption of cheese worldwide in 2022 (in kilograms), by country (Statista, 2023)

OECD/FAO (2023) is predicting a significant increase in consumption by 2032, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 : Per Capita Cheese Consumption per region and Forecasts (OECD/FAO, 2023).

Increased disposable income, population growth, and knowledge of the link between food and health are the main causes of this rise in dairy product consumption, especially in North America, Europe and central Asia, and to a lesser extent, the Near East and North Africa (NENA). Fresh dairy products are consumed in low- and middle-income countries, such as the NENA region, while processed dairy products, such as processed cheeses, are consumed by the majority in North America and the European Union. This can be explained in part by their practicality, ability to be preserved, and use in cuisine, especially in fast food.

Growing demand for cheeses from small ruminants is supported by an increased awareness among consumers towards their health benefits. Sheep and goat cheeses are perceived as healthier by consumers than cheese manufactured from cow's milk. Indeed, sheep's cheese is higher in calcium, magnesium, vitamin B12, vitamin C, and folate, compared to goat cheese. People who have trouble digesting cow milk may often tolerate sheep milk cheese. However since sheep milk contains lactose, those who are lactose sensitive might not want to consume it. Goat cheese is also a popular choice among health-conscious consumers because of its high calcium content and other vitamins and minerals, as well as its low cholesterol and lactose contents, making it a better alternative for those who are lactose intolerant. Several surveys have been conducted in order to evaluate consumer perceptions and preferences toward cheeses from small ruminants. Vargas-Bello-Pérez et al. (2022) have reported a high consumption of dairy products from sheep and goats, in Italy (90.7% of respondents), Spain (89.9%), and Greece (80.4%), when compared to Latin American nations (Chile and Mexico), and Bangladesh. In this survey, respondents from Italy (50.5% of respondents), Spain (53.8%), and Greece (69.1%).declared having no preference between goat and sheep dairy products, whereas about 30% of respondents stated a preference for sheep products over goat ones. Greece, Spain, and Italy were the Mediterranean countries with the greatest consumption frequency of cheese from small ruminants. Consumption was limited to two or three times per month in Latin American countries (Chile and Mexico), whereas it was one to two times per year in Bangladesh, or when needed because of illness. In the USA, Colby (2021) has reported that 20% of survey respondents declared having recently consumed cheese made from goat or sheep milk. Main drivers were features promoting aspects of physical and emotional well-being, lifestyle, experience, ethics and values. In Tunisia, Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023) have conducted a survey in the

metropolitan region of Greater Tunis (Tunisia) on 318 respondents (81.7% women ; 18.3% men). Most of those surveyed (96.3% of respondents) are regular consumers of cheese. A majority (75.7%) of the panel says they prefer national cheeses. However, only 39.4% of panelists say they consume sheep's cheese, on a daily basis (23.3% of sheep's cheese consumers) and weekly (36.0%). The main reasons are the appreciation of the typical sensory characteristics of sheep's cheese (77.9%), a higher product quality than that of cow's cheese (37.3%) and the health benefits (25.6%). Sheep cheese purchases are based on sensory attributes (93%), product price (44.2%), geographic origin of the product (38.4%), product certification (26.7%) and packaging (9.3%).

Nonetheless, one of the constraints impeding the increase in consumption of sheep and goat cheeses is the high price of these dairy products.

1.3 Cheese Market

The global cheese market has reached 83.4 billion US dollars (USD) in 2022. The Industry ARC (2022) prediction for 2023 is that it may reach USD 120.2 billion by 2028, indicating a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.12% from 2023 to 2028. Cheese manufacturing is mostly concentrated around 20% processed cheese and 80% fresh cheese (Mozzarella, Cheddar, Feta, Parmesan, Roquefort, Others) in terms of segmentation.

More specifically, the global sheep milk cheese market is expected to reach USD 3,240 million by 2027, rising at a 4.9% annual rate, between 2022 and 2027, according to Industry ARC (2022). These projections are based on rising demand for sheep cheese as a healthy food option; increased knowledge of sheep cheese's health advantages; growing interest in artisanal and specialty cheeses, more sheep cheese products available at supermarkets and grocery stores and creation of internet retail platforms that sell sheep's cheese. However, sheep's milk is more expensive than cow's milk because sheep produce less milk. As a result of increased demand and limited supply, the price of sheep's milk rises, affecting the price of sheep's milk cheese.

Similarly, the global goat cheese market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 4.8% from USD 8670 million in 2021 to USD 13 217 million, according to PS Intelligence (2022). The two main drivers are the growing demand from customers for artisanal and specialized goods as well as the health benefits of goat cheese. Rising demand for goat cheese products in developed economies such as the United States and EU is expected to drive retail sales (Mordor Intelligence, 2023). As the world's largest consumer and producer of goat cheese, Europe is witnessing a notable expansion in the goat cheese sector. The two biggest markets for goat cheese in the EU are France and Germany. Africa and Asia are among the regions that consume the most goat milk, but consuming less goat cheese than developed countries. However, the rising prevalence of obesity and cholesterol-related disorders in these areas is expected to increase demand for goat cheese (Mordor Intelligence, 2023). The main growth constraints impacting the goat cheese industry are its pricier cost in comparison to cheeses made from cow's milk, the scarcity of raw materials, the lack of customer familiarity, the challenge of cultivating a taste for it, and the fact that there are less possibilities than for other kinds of cheese.

Based on distribution channels, the sheep and goat cheese market may be further divided into four segments: supermarkets, specialty retailers, convenience stores, and e-commerce (Industry ARC, 2022; Mordor Intelligence, 2023). In 2022, in developed countries, the segment with the most market share was the supermarkets. This development may be attributed to a number of drivers, including the disponibility of these cheese varieties, which encourages people to purchase these products in supermarkets. Moreover, due to people's current preference for online shopping and the fact that they don't have the time to visit stores because of their busy schedules, the E-Commerce segment is predicted to grow faster (Industry ARC, 2022; Mordor Intelligence, 2023). This is because people are using more online channels to purchase a wider range of goods in this advanced technological era.

According to Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023), the marketing of sheep and goat cheeses in the North of Tunisia is also based on multimodal distribution systems. Sheep cheese producers essentially use two channels which differ depending on the mode of cheese production, artisanal or semi-industrial:

Channel 1: Direct sales (100% of survey respondents) is a two-step process (producer, consumer), and is carried out through sales points on the farm or in town (mainly in Béja), via social networks or a web merchant site or in local markets.

Channel 2: Semi-wholesale sales (75% of respondents) are characterized by the fact that the cheesemaker provides one or more points of sale throughout Tunisia, and particularly the North and the coastal regions (Nabeul, Sousse, Sfax): delicatessens, creameries, grocery stores, markets in Greater Tunis, hotels, restaurants, restaurants and guest houses.

In addition to these distribution channels, some breeders-processors offer an agritourism offer as a complement to their activity, and as a marketing strategy for the promotion of local food products. Indeed, agrotourism (or rural tourism) is closely linked to the environmentally friendly and healthful reputation of sheep and goat traditional products (European Parliament, 2017). According to Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023), this agrotourism offer in the sheep dairy sector in the North of Tunisia offers several activities:

- Visit to the farm and to the cheese processing workshop;
- The table d'hôte, promoting local gastronomy and local products, in particular sheep or goat cheese;
- A point of sale for cheese and local products mainly from the farm.

Agrotourism leads not only to emphasize the region of origin and breeding, but also to strengthen the local economy (European Parliament, 2017).

1.4 Regulations

Health standards and quality of dairy products are essential to ensure food safety and consumer satisfaction.

According to International Dairy Federation, dairy products can be tested for:

- Quantity – measured in volume or weight
- Organoleptic characteristics – appearance, taste and smell
- Compositional characteristics – especially fat, solid and protein contents
- Physical and chemical characteristics
- Hygienic characteristics – hygienic conditions, cleanliness and quality
- Drug residues
- Adulteration – with water, preservatives, added solids, etc.

Milk and dairy products of high quality must be free of debris and sediment, free of off-flavors, color, and odor, low in bacterial count, free of chemicals (e.g., antibiotics, detergents), and of normal composition and acidity. To accomplish this, testing and quality control should be performed at all stages of the dairy supply chain.

The Codex Alimentarius has published a series of standards applicable to cheeses made from cow's milk, goat's milk or sheep's milk and mixtures of these milks. Codex Cheese Standards are:

- CODEX STAN 283-1978 NORME GÉNÉRALE CODEX POUR LE FROMAGE Revised in 1999. Amended in 2006, 2008, 2010, 2013, 2018, 2021, 2022. 2022 Amendment.
- CXS 208-1999 GROUP STANDARD FOR CHEESES IN BRINE adopted in 1999. Amended in 2001, 2010, 2018, 2021.
- CXS 221-2001 GROUP STANDARD FOR UNRIPENED CHEESE INCLUDING FRESH CHEESE Adopted in 2001. Amended in 2008, 2010, 2013, 2018, 2021, 2022. 2022 Amendment
- CXS 278-1978 STANDARD FOR EXTRA HARD GRATING CHEESE Adopted in 1978. Amended in 2018, 2021, 2022. 2022 Amendment
- CXS 206-1999 GENERAL STANDARD FOR THE USE OF DAIRY TERMS
- CAC/GL 67-2008 MODEL EXPORT CERTIFICATE FOR MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS

In addition, Codex texts relevant for milk and milk products are:

- CXS 193-1995 GENERAL STANDARD FOR CONTAMINANTS AND TOXINS IN FOOD AND FEED Adopted in 1995 Revised in 1997, 2006, 2008, 2009 Amended in 2010, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019
- CODEX STAN 192-1995 GENERAL STANDARD FOR FOOD ADDITIVES Adopted in 1995. Revision 1997, 1999, 2001, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021
- CXS 234-1999 RECOMMENDED METHODS OF ANALYSIS AND SAMPLING
- CX/MRL 2-2021 MAXIMUM RESIDUE LIMITS (MRLs) AND RISK MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS (RMRs) FOR RESIDUES OF VETERINARY DRUGS IN FOODS
- CODEX PESTICIDES RESIDUES IN FOOD ONLINE DATABASE: <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/codex-texts/dbs/pestres/pesticides/en/>

The hygiene and health quality of cheeses are governed by a series of Codex General Texts For Milk And Milk Products:

- CAC/RCP 57-2004 CODE OF HYGIENIC PRACTICE FOR MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS CXC 1-1969 GENERAL PRINCIPLES OF FOOD HYGIENE Adopted in 1969. Amended in 1999. Revised in 1997, 2003, 2020, 2022*.
- CAC/GL 60-2006 PRINCIPLES APPLICABLE TO TRACEABILITY/PRODUCT TRACING AS A TOOL OF A FOOD INSPECTION AND CERTIFICATION SYSTEM
- CXG 21-1997 PRINCIPLES AND GUIDELINES FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND APPLICATION OF MICROBIOLOGICAL CRITERIA FOR FOODS. Amended in 2013

Furthermore, cheese processing units are subject to veterinary health approval. It is an approval “authorizing the production, processing, handling and storage of products of animal origin or foodstuffs containing these products”. In Europe, European health approval allows companies to market their products throughout Europe. It makes it easier for the processor to distribute its dairy products in the different distribution channels (farm sales, market, producer stores, supermarkets, collective catering, etc.) without limits on volume and distance. The EU reference texts in terms of health approval are the texts of the Hygiene Package and more particularly:

- Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002 is the key text of the Hygiene Package: the Food Law. It lays down the general principles of the regulatory corpus and is applicable to all players in the sector. It specifies in particular the responsibilities of food sector operators in terms of food safety, traceability and management of non-conformities.
- Regulation (EC) No. 852/2004 on food hygiene is applicable to all food business operators: whether at the primary production, processing or distribution stage; and whatever the production sectors. It requires, among other things, the implementation of procedures based on HACCP principles.
- Regulation (EC) No. 853/2004 laying down specific hygiene rules applicable to foodstuffs of animal origin is applicable to all food sector operators handling or processing animal foodstuffs or foodstuffs of animal origin. It specifies the approval requirement and provides technical specifications by sector in Annex III.

The European health approval contains the Health Control Plan, which describes all the good practices that the processor implements on a daily basis to ensure that its products do not endanger the consumers health. It mentions:

- Workshop plan
- Staff training
- HACCP hazard analysis
- Cleaning plan for premises and equipment
- Traceability
- Management of non-conformities

In Tunisia, the terms of granting are regulated by the Minister of Agriculture, JORT of May 26, 2006, setting out the terms of veterinary health control, the conditions and procedures for granting health approval, establishments producing, processing and packaging animal products.

Challenges of small ruminants dairy sector

2.1 Environmental challenges

The sheep and goat dairy sector faces several environmental challenges which result from the complex interaction between agricultural practices, climatic conditions and economic pressures. Sheep and goat breeding systems impose environmental pressures traditionally associated with intensive livestock farming. Moreover, goats and sheeps contribute significantly to climate change in particular because of enteric methane emissions and the pollution generated by livestock farming: in terms of sustainability, the production of fodder crops and livestock breeding constitute the main points of environmental impacts throughout the ruminant production chain. Poux et al. (2009) listed breeding practices that may have an environmental impact (Table 7).

Sheep and goat farming has positive impacts on the environment, as reported by Poux et al. (2009). They are related in particular to their ethological and physiological characteristics which allow them to exploit environments difficult for other animals, particularly cattle, which are more demanding. Indeed, small ruminants have the capacity to graze and exploit plant formations ranging from the steppe to the Mediterranean scrubland. In addition, the parturition and lactation period is reduced (from 3 to 4 months), which notably limits the water requirement of the herds and allows adaptation to arid environments. They also have the ability to travel over long distances without loss of productivity. These characteristics make sheep and goats privileged users of “bad lands” in geographical contexts ranging from the heather moors of Northern Europe to the Mediterranean maquis and scrublands.

Table 7. Environmental impact of breeding practices from Poux et al. (2009).

Practice	Type	Negative Impact on Environment	Positive Impact on Environment
Herd management	Above ground	-Water pollution -No landscape management	
	Unguarded sedentary and penned herd	± Risk of water pollution (moderate) - Risk of under/overgrazing - Risk of large predator conflicts	+ Landscape management
	Sedentary guarded by shepherd		+ Landscape management + Low risk of pollution of under/overgrazing water (see below) due to straying and concentration of animals and conflicts large predators
	Transhumant pastoral (guarded)		+ Same as above
Loading	Undergrazing	- Risks of abandonment and closure of landscapes, loss of biodiversity and fire risks - Risks of soil erosion and loss of biodiversity	
	Overgrazing		
	Optimal loading (function of guarding and/or park management: rotation, periods, etc.)		+ Balance pressure and capacity of the environment, maintenance of the landscape
Fodder system	Semi-natural vegetation (including poorly fertilized grasslands) in extensive systems		+ Biodiversity and landscapes + Climate change (CC) (carbon storage)
	Productive and intensified herding		+ Landscapes ± Biodiversity + CC (C storage)
	Temporary grassland meadows		+ Landscapes ± CC (C storage)
	Fodder crops	- Biodiversity	+ Landscapes ± Biodiversity ± CC (restitution of soil organic matter, less fertilizer used)
Fire management	Fire controlled on pastures	- CC (but impacts limited by surface burning) - Biodiversity	+ Landscape + Biodiversity
	Uncontrolled fire	- CC (major) - Landscape - Biodiversity	
	Fire prevention (see loading)		+ CC (major) + Landscape + Biodiversity
Miscellaneous	Carcasses of dead animals left for scavengers	- Health risks (punctual)	+ Biodiversity
	Maintenance of rural architectural heritage (including terraces)		+ Landscape and erosion; biodiversity

Negative environmental impacts are mainly related to herd management and loading. Intensification strategies are notably based on the use of fodder, because feed alone constitutes 60 to 70% of the cost of milk production. The increase in livestock numbers puts strong pressure on the total quantity of food and fodder available, due to the stagnation of fodder production and areas for rangelands (Elloumi et al., 2011).

- **Climate change**

Climate change is one of the most important issues affecting the sector. Mediterranean countries are particularly vulnerable to the effects of climate change, such as increased temperatures, more frequent periods of drought and extreme weather events (INM, 2023). Increased temperature and lower precipitation can have a direct negative impact on herd health and performance, and an indirect negative impact on the availability of food resources, including pasture and water management. At the animal level, increased temperature and radiation cause heat stress, which triggers behavioral and metabolic changes affecting animal health and well-being (Marino et al., 2016). Indeed, reproductive performance could be impaired not only by reduced sperm production and changes in male sexual activity, but also by a lower conception rate of females and lighter birth weight of lambs (Indu and Pareek, 2015; Marino et al., 2016). Furthermore, heat stress is generally associated with low food intake, and therefore reduced performance. It also alters the immune responses of animals (Sevi and Caroprese, 2012). Finally, milk production could be reduced by 20 to 30%, with lower concentrations of proteins (especially caseins) and fats, a reduction in the content of unsaturated fatty acids, and a reduction in the coagulation properties of milk (Sevi and Caroprese, 2012).

- **Animal Food Supply**

In terms of animal food supply, climate change will have deleterious effects on the quantity, reliability and quality of forage production, water demand for growing forage crops, and vegetation patterns (Giridhar and Samireddypalle, 2015; Cheng et al., 2022). The most visible effect of climate change concerns the primary productivity of forage crops and rangelands (Wheeler and Reynolds, 2013). Southern Mediterranean countries are more vulnerable to climate change than other developed countries due to the predominance of agriculture in their economies and their warmer climates, as well as their limited resources to adapt to new technologies (Giridhar and Samireddypalle, 2015). According to INM projections, by 2050, crops and forage plants will be subject to warmer temperatures, high levels of carbon dioxide, as well as extremely fluctuating water availability due to the evolution of precipitation regimes. The interaction between these factors will determine the actual impact on plant growth and yield (Giridhar and Samireddypalle, 2015). Elevated CO₂ levels are likely to alter forage crop yields and pasture composition and forage production (Wheeler and Reynolds, 2013; Cheng et al., 2022). Increased temperature associated with high CO₂ levels will affect forage quality. Productivity and quality of forage and cereals under rainfed conditions are expected to decrease (Wheeler and Reynolds, 2013). On the other hand, the increase in temperature will lead to a decrease in water availability and an increase in its consumption. The agricultural sector being the largest user of freshwater resources, the reduction in water reserves will have a negative impact on the production of fodder crops. Heat and water stress could alter the timing and length of the plant growing season. Natural rangelands and crop residues constitute the

main fodder resources for goat and sheep farming in Mediterranean countries. Currently, for instance, fodder availability is insufficient to feed the Tunisian sheep herd, in particular because of increased drought. Finally, projections predict that increased temperature and changes in precipitation patterns will lead to increased stress caused by diseases, pests and parasites (Cheng et al., 2022).

Economic pressures to increase milk production can lead to intensification of livestock farming, with potentially negative consequences for the environment. Indeed, the expansion of small ruminant farming has induced the loss of biodiversity as well as the degradation, fragmentation and destruction of natural habitats. More particularly, the intensification of production systems, the sedentarization of animals and the end of transhumance explain these enormous pressures on resources, due to overgrazing, as well as overloading and degradation of rangelands and environmental pollution, with ultimately negative consequences for biodiversity. The impact of livestock on the ground can be classified into two main categories, the physical impact of the animal on the ground when it moves on the one hand and on the other hand, the chemical and biological impact of excrement and urine that the animal deposits on the ground (Singh & Rashid, 2017). Intensive grazing systems can therefore lead to: (1) soil degradation due to reduced vegetation cover, productivity and litter accumulation, destruction of topsoil structure and compaction of soil. soil resulting from trampling, (2) a reduction in their soil fertility, (3) an alteration of the vegetation cover, (4) an aggravation of erosion and (5) an increase in the surface of bare soil it is that is, desertification, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions. In fact, unsustainable or intensive use of pastures can result in:

- a degradation of local biodiversity and plant cover,
- worsening erosion,
- a reduction in soil fertility,
- disruption of natural ecosystems
- competition with other land uses (Alkemade et al. 2013).

This unsustainable and/or intensive management therefore constitutes a serious threat to biodiversity. The diversity of plant species plays a role in the functioning of pasture ecosystems. However, the reduction in herbaceous cover due to unsustainable and/or intensive use of pastures can encourage the development of woody type vegetation, replacing annual grasses, in the competition for access to water resources.

- **Water Resources**

Mediterranean countries are subject to periods of drought and limited water availability. The agricultural sector's pressure on water resources is significant (79% of the overall volume). Therefore, this water stress directly affects food security. Sheep and goat farming requires a significant amount of water for watering animals in order to maintain their health, milk production and well-being: on average, 5 to 13 L/d depending on several factors, including temperature, production stage of the ewe, pregnancy, lactation, feed quality, and access to drinking water. Small ruminant milk is approximately 81% water. Sheep and goats are tolerant of water restrictions (Tulu et al., 2023). Casamassima et al. (2008) observed that a restriction of 20 to 40% in winter affects neither feed intake nor milk productivity in intensive farming nor milk quality. On the other hand, water stress, coupled with heat stress, can lead to a weakening of food intake, weight loss, an increase in cooling

by evaporation through panting, a reduction in the production and quality of urine (very concentrated), hemoconcentration, an increase in blood osmolarity and an alteration of immune responses (Chedid et al., 2014; Tulu et al., 2023). Additionally, prolonged water scarcity can affect birth weight and survival of lambs and goat kids, and reduced reproduction (Chedid et al., 2014; Tulu et al., 2023). In addition to water availability during periods of drought, there is the problem of water quality, linked to an increase in salt concentration. For instance, projections in Tunisia predict that losses by salinization of coastal water tables due to sea level rise would be around 50% of current resources, by 2030, or nearly 150 million m³ (MARHP, 2020). In this context, animals undergo physiological, blood, biochemical, dietary and water changes but adapt to the salinity levels of drinking water in arid environments (Tulu et al., 2023). Finally, the availability of water resources can also affect food production for sheep and goat flocks, and thus compromise the quality of livestock feed. Water management practices for pasture irrigation and drinking water supply must therefore be sustainable to avoid depletion of water resources.

- **Water and soil pollution**

Small ruminant farming can cause water and soil pollution, the factors are inadequate management of waste from sheep production, such as manure (2.5 kg/day) and livestock effluents, pesticides. such as chemicals used to soak sheepskins, and microbial contamination (by *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium*), as well as toxic substances such as antibiotics, hormones and veterinary medical residues (EPA 2015). Excess nutrients (i.e., nitrate and phosphorus) in the environment can contribute to eutrophication of streams and aquatic ecosystems and soil acidification (EPA 2015). Furthermore, the increase in the concentration of ammonia in the atmosphere leads to the formation of fine particles, eutrophication and acidification of soils and water surfaces, causing damage to ecosystems, and reducing the plant biodiversity. Singh and Rashid (2017) reported that significant fractions (typically >90%) of heavy metals present in livestock feed are excreted in manure, and can lead to their accumulation in plants and also leaching to the Surface and groundwater can have negative effects on the health of aquatic ecosystems.

Additionally, pests and diseases can negatively affect the yield and longevity of herbaceous and forage crops. However, the excessive use of inputs such as fertilizers and pesticides can have harmful effects on soil and water resources: for instance, in Tunisia it has caused edaphic, atmospheric and aquatic pollution, including soil contamination, groundwater and surface water by nitrates and phosphates, as well as pesticide residues (Benabdelkader et al., 2021; Necibi et al., 2022).

- **Genetic resources**

Genetic improvement of herds is essential to increase milk production and milk quality. The implementation of management programs in reproduction and genetic improvement has become one of the main actions of the sheep and goat dairy sector in the countries of the North and South of the Mediterranean. Its objective is not only to preserve biodiversity and fight against the effects of climate change but above all to improve the performance and productivity of animals. Indeed, the processes of intensification and standardization of global agricultural production have generated a certain standardization of animal and plant species. Consequently, 90% of the proteins currently consumed in the world by populations are produced by only 14 animal species. Milk production constitutes the main parameter affecting the profitability of the dairy sector and this is why breeding

programs have long considered milk production as the main selection criterion. Genetic diversity within species and between populations constitutes one of the components of biodiversity: SDG 2.5 of the United Nations 2030 Agenda (2015) seeks to address concerns about the genetic diversity of plant and animal species domesticated animals and their relatives. It is the main tool for adaptability and survival of species over several generations, and today in the face of climate change which has become an essential player in natural selection (United Nations, 2015). For instance, in Tunisia, the Sicilian-Sardinian sheep breed is characterized by tolerance to extreme climatic conditions and resistance to disease. However, it is currently threatened and considered a priority in terms of conservation of endangered indigenous animal genetic resources by the National Gene Bank of Tunisia (Aloulou et al., 2018). According to Pardo & Del Prado (2020), inclusion of heat tolerance traits in current small ruminant selection programs may provide a useful tool for establishing climate-oriented farming systems in Europe and Mediterranean countries. However, authors raised difficulties in defining heat tolerance criteria and quantifying adequate levels for the selected traits. Overall, each production system must value an equilibrium between productivity and adaptation to high heat loads in selection or crossbreeding programs.

- **Animal diseases and pests**

Climate change has both direct and indirect effects on livestock productivity, not only through changes in precipitation patterns, drought, extreme weather episodes, but also through geographic redistribution, prevalence and seasonality of pests, microorganisms and parasites, their vectors and diseases (FAO, 2020). In fact, the incidence, spread and predictability of animal diseases are affected by the effects of climate change (FAO, 2020). Increasing temperatures have a greater impact on the life cycle of pathogens, contributing in particular to shortening the development cycle and incubation period of these agents and extending survival, thus favoring the transmission of infections (Wanjala et al., 2022). Actually plant-borne helminth infections (due to gastrointestinal nematodes and liver fluke) constitute one of the most serious health and productivity issues in sheep farms around the world (Pardo & Del Prado, 2020). Diseases, microorganisms and parasites can have a significant impact on the health of flocks, including compromising the animals' immune status and reproductive performance and affecting milk production (Pardo & Del Prado, 2020). Effective animal health management requires investments in veterinary surveillance, adequate health care and preventive measures. Pardo & Del Prado (2020) have proposed guidelines for small ruminant production systems as a mitigation strategy of climate change impacts in Europe.

To conclude this part, it is critical to adopt sustainable and environmentally friendly agricultural and farming practices in order to address these environmental challenges. Growing sustainability concerns, such as waste management, reducing environmental footprint, and animal welfare, require adaptation and adoption of more environmentally and socially responsible practices by the sheep dairy industry. They should center on pastoralism and sustainable rangeland management, as well as the interdependence of breeders, their herds, and the environments they exploit. This could also include the installation of efficient irrigation systems, pasture rotation, the promotion of agroecology and permaculture, and the education of livestock breeders about sustainable management practices. It is also critical to invest in agricultural digitalization while ensuring an inclusive and long-term approach for all stakeholders. FAO (2020) recently proposed various climate change mitigation options for livestock management, such as flexible grazing, alternative feeds (by-products, crop

residues, alternative fodder), alternative feeding practices (increased number of meals, targeted supplementation, etc.), landscaping and stabling (to provide shelter, water, shade, etc.), the selection of adapted animal and plant genetics, the increase in biodiversity of the component animals and plants, the introduction of new reproduction techniques. A comprehensive and collaborative approach by governments, researchers, farmers, and industry stakeholders is required to find regionally appropriate solutions.

2.2 Safety, Quality and Authenticity Challenges

The safety and authenticity of milk and its products are becoming increasingly important and concerns as a result of rising milk production worldwide. When a consumer's health is at danger due to contamination by physical, chemical, or biological factors or to adulteration, milk and milk products may no longer be safe.

2.2.1 Food safety

In order to access markets and satisfy consumers, producers must comply with local and international standards, as well as establish traceability and quality control systems. Given the microbiological fragility of milk, quality control extends to all points along the dairy supply chain, from production to marketing, where contamination can occur as shown in Figure 9. In fact, the risk of bacterial contamination is widely regarded as high.

Figure 9. Simplified dairy supply chain identifying areas of contamination in the primary and processing stages from Montgomery et al. (2020; <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211912420301012>)

Consumption of milk and dairy products presents a zoonotic risk from the primary stages of production (van den Brom et al., 2020). Most pathogenic microorganisms found in milk are linked to more milk-producing animal species. Ganter (2015) have reviewed zoonotic risks from small ruminants: most zoonotic diseases diagnosed in sheep and goats are transmitted through close contact between humans and these animals and are more commonly occupational diseases, primarily affecting breeders, veterinarians, and/or slaughterhouse workers. Some other diseases are airborne and affect the population near sheep/goat farms.

Raw milk can be contaminated either by endogenous transfer (i.e., direct transfer of blood or by infection in the udder), or/and by exogenous transfer (i.e., during or after the milking process). Van den Brom et al. (2020) have reviewed main microorganisms found milk:

- Bacteria, like *Brucella melitensis*, pathogenic *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria* spp., and *Salmonella* spp. as most frequently described in sheep and goat milk,
- Fungi, mainly causing bovine, but also described as cause of ovine mastitis,
- Parasites, with *Toxoplasma gondii* as main hazard,
- Viruses that can be transmitted from sheep and goat milk to humans like tick borne encephalitis virus (TBEV) and Rift Valley fever virus (RVFV).

According to the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC, 2023), in 2021, 29 EU/EEA countries reported overall:

- 165 confirmed cases of brucellosis, with an overall rate of 0.04 per 100,000 populations. No cases were reported by twelve Member States. The countries with the most confirmed cases were Italy, Spain, Greece, and France, which accounted for 67% of all cases reported in the EU/EEA.
- 463 confirmed cases of *Coxiella burnetii* responsible for Fever Q, mostly in Spain (31% of cases), followed by Germany (21%) and France (19%).
- a notification rate of 73 per 100,000 population for *Chlamydia*.

In Tunisia, concerning the prevalence of brucellosis between 2005 and 2018 notified by the veterinary services to the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE), the national animal health monitoring center (2020) reported a total of 305 outbreaks counting 2123 cases of brucellosis in small ruminants. Concerning the germs responsible for abortion in sheep, an epidemiological survey carried out in the north of Tunisia (Elandalousi et al. 2015) showed prevalence in sheep of *Coxiella burnetii* (56.84%), *Chlamydia* (3.15 %) and *Brucella* (1.05%).

Bluetongue (BT) is a vector-borne viral disease that causes variable clinical signs in ruminants, including sheep and goats, depending on the species and breed. It is an OIE listed disease. The EU has implemented surveillance, eradication programs including vaccination for this disease (EC, 2023), that have limited the spread of disease and led to zones with disease-free status (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Bluetongue status in EU-27 (EU, 2023).

In Tunisia, Kalthoum et al. (2022) have highlighted a high seroprevalence of bluetongue disease viruses (40.1%), in sheep throughout Tunisia.

At the processing stages, there have been several reports in the literature of toxic infections caused by pathogenic germs. In Europe, the EU Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) database is a tool monitoring any safety issues for milk and milk products: between 2013 and October 2023, 155 notifications related to cheese and hazards, mostly biological, were published: 27 concerning goat cheese and 12 sheep cheese. This represented 1.29% from the total E.U. food notifications for this last decade (2013-10/2023). According to meta-analysis of Gonzales-Barron et al. (2017), there is a scarcity of current data on pathogen incidence in goat and sheep raw milk and cheeses, particularly for *Salmonella* and *L. monocytogenes* in raw cheeses. However, these raw milks contain significant pathogenic contamination. Gonzales-Barron et al. (2017) have also reported that pathogens are more prevalent in goat milk cheeses (9.83%; 95% CI: 5.82-16.1%) than in sheep milk cheeses (2.94%; 1.32-6.45%). In particular, Shiga-toxin producing *Escherichia coli* was found in goat milk cheeses at a higher rate (4.31%; 95% CI: 1.78-10.0%) than in sheep milk cheeses (2.76%; 95% CI: 1.09-6.79%). In the European Union (EU), cheese consumption led to 2.2% of collective foodborne illnesses reported in 2017 (EFSA et al., 2018). They were caused by several pathogenic microorganisms, mainly *Salmonella* spp, *Campylobacter* spp, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Escherichia coli* (Yoon et al., 2016). In the United States, 38 cases of toxic infections were due to the consumption of raw milk cheeses between 1998 and 2011 (O'Sullivan et al., 2017). The EFSA (2017) reported a 3%

increase in human cases of salmonellosis between 2014 and 2016 (94,530 cases in 2016) representing an increase of 3%. However this risk was considered to be low in dairy products (0.1% detection on more than 25,000 samples tested) compared to that inherent in the consumption of poultry and egg products. On the other hand, *S. aureus* is the most common microorganism responsible for mastitis compared to *L. monocytogenes*, *E. coli* and *Salmonella*, which are rarer. In 2017, the presence of *S. aureus* was reported in various animals and food products in six EU Member States and two non-EU Member States (EFSA, 2018). It is commonly detected in products made from raw milk, but the probability of production of enterotoxins by the strains is variable (AFSCA, 2015). In the United States, the consumption of raw milk cheeses is the cause of 11% of the 38 cases of poisoning caused by *E. coli* between 1998 and 2011 (O’Sullivan et al., 2017). Infection with Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* can have serious consequences on the health of consumers and can develop into hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS) for up to 10% of patients, with a mortality rate of 3 to 5% (O’Sullivan et al., 2017). Furthermore, campylobacteriosis has been reported as the most commonly reported foodborne illness in the EU since 2005 (EFSA, 2015): 246,307 people were infected in 2016. Listeriosis causes a more severe infection: 97% of patients from these at-risk populations are hospitalized following contamination. This disease is continually increasing: between 2013 and 2014, an increase of 13% was observed (EFSA, 2015). In 2016, 2536 cases were reported and 247 deaths reported. Certain categories of people are more likely to be affected by *L. monocytogenes*, such as the elderly, children, pregnant women and immunocompromised individuals (Lopez-Valladares et al., 2018).

In Tunisia, Jarboui et al. (2023) showed compliance of 83% of industrial dairy products studied while showing that this rate was only 43% for products manufactured in an artisanal manner. These results are explained by the lack of hygiene and lack of awareness among employees working on the farm (i.e. hygiene, milking practices) and those involved in milk processing. On the other hand, *Brucella* has been detected in artisanal dairy products in the Béja region (Bejaoui et al., 2022).

This risk of the presence of these pathogens can be reduced by good management of herd health, prevention of contamination during milking and proper processing, transport and storage of milk. However, in small-scale production systems, the risk is higher than in industrialized production systems due to a less protocolized and controlled production process.

The fight against zoonoses must be carried out within the framework of an integrative “One Health” approach. In Europe, European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the ECDC publish annually an European One Health zoonoses report, providing data on zoonoses, zoonotic agents, antimicrobial resistance, and food-borne outbreaks (FBO) covered by the Zoonoses Directive 2003/99/EC. “One Health” approach through surveillance systems, is implemented not only for early warning, detection, or occurrence of infection purposes but mainly to prevent human infections. In Tunisia, the Ministry of Agriculture has set up a free vaccination program to combat brucellosis, foot and mouth disease, claudication and blue tongue according to a pre-established schedule. It also distributed ministerial circular No. 190 of October 19, 2020 relating to the measures to be put in place for the prevention and fight against bluetongue disease and organized disinfestation campaigns in stables.

2.2.2 Cheese Authenticity

Sheep's and goat's cheese are one of the most adulterated food products in the world, due to fraudulent production practices (adding cow's milk) and false labels on the origin of the product.

The *Prevention of Food Adulteration Act* (1954) considers a food article as adulterated:

- if the article sold by a vendor is not of the nature, substance, or quality demanded by the purchaser and is to his prejudice, or is not of the nature, substance, or quality which it purports or represented to be;
- if the article contains any other substance which affects, or if the article is so processed as to affect, injuriously the nature, substance or quality thereof;
- if any inferior or cheaper substance has been substituted wholly or in part for the article to affect injuriously the nature, substance or quality thereof;
- if any constituent of the article has been wholly or in part abstracted to affect injuriously the nature, substance or quality thereof;
- if the article had been prepared, packed, or kept under insanitary conditions whereby it has become contaminated or injurious to health;
- if the article consists wholly or in part of any filthy, putrid, rotten, decomposed, or diseased animal or vegetable substance or is insect-infested or is otherwise unfit for human consumption;
- if the article is obtained from a diseased animal;
- if the article contains any poisonous or other ingredients which renders it injurious to health;
- if the container of the article is composed, whether wholly or in part, of any poisonous or deleterious substance which renders its contents injurious to health;
- if any coloring matter other than that prescribed in respect thereof is present in the article, or if the amounts of the prescribed coloring matter which is present in the article are not within the prescribed limits of variability;
- if the article contains any prohibited preservative or permitted preservative above the prescribed limits;
- if the quality or purity of the article falls below the prescribed standard or its constituents are present in quantities not within the prescribed limits of variability, which render it injurious to health;
- if the quality or purity of the article falls below the prescribed standard or its constituents are present in quantities not within the prescribed limits of variability but which does not render it injurious to health.

In addition to its negative socio-economic impacts, this food fraud undermines not only the safety and quality of food, but also its authenticity. The PRIMA MEDIFIT project (2020-2023) is particularly interested in this issue. Concerning fraud on sheep's milk, according to our interviews, the main fraud consists of mixing it with cow's milk, without indicating it on the product labeling. In Europe, RASFF alerts from 2015 to 2019 have reported inadequate controls: 5 related to fraud/adulteration and 3

labeling issues. One report was on feta cheese made with 100% cow's milk rather than the label's specified 70% sheep milk and 30% goat milk.

In Tunisia, the problem of fraud is a concerning issue for 85% of the processors surveyed and 72% of creamers. No official control is carried out on the origin of the milk (cow/sheep) nor on the compliance of the labeling (made with cow/sheep milk) with national regulations. In order to assess the perception of Tunisian consumers with regard to the falsification of sheep's cheese, a survey was conducted in the metropolitan region of Greater Tunis (Tunisia) in 2022 on 318 respondents (81.7% women; 18.3% men). Most of those surveyed (96.3%) are regular consumers of cheese. However, only 39.4% of panelists say they consume sheep's cheese, daily (23.3% of sheep's cheese consumers) and weekly (36.0% of consumers). Around 67% of respondents were concerned about cheese adulteration. For 47%, this food fraud constitutes a major problem in Tunisia, and for 43% this sector is not well regulated. Around 72% say they are confident in the authenticity of their purchase. To guarantee the authenticity and safety of the cheese, the people interviewed relied on the reputation of the producers (73.3%), sensory characteristics (55.8%), certification (40.7%), labeling information (38.4%), merchant awareness (29.1%) and price (20.9%).

Labeling fraud is particularly widespread throughout the world. Labels are a mandatory element of food product packaging, aimed at providing information on food quality and traceability to consumers. Depending on the marketing method (cheese sold in individual portions or by the cut), the labeling differs. Tunisian regulation for pre-packaged products describes individual labeling (JORT of the Ministry of Commerce of September 3, 2008 relating to the labeling and presentation of pre-packaged foodstuffs).

According to article 10, it must include:

- the name of the cheese as well as the animal species if it is not made from cow's milk;
- the list of ingredients, if other ingredients other than milk, lactic ferments, rennet and salt have been added: for example, spices, pepper;
- the mention of the fat content;
- the net quantity;
- the date of manufacture;
- the date of minimum durability, in the case of very microbiologically perishable foodstuffs, or the expiration date as well as the indication of the particular conditions of conservation and use,
- the name or company name and address of the producer or farm;
- the batch number;
- the place of origin or provenance;
- allergens (article 21);
- possibly, the storage temperature.

Abedini et al. (2023) have reviewed some frauds/adulterations on cheese that they have illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Main frauds/adulterations on cheese: from Abedini et al. (2023)

According to Abedini et al. (2023), the most frequent frauds in cheese that were recorded were mixing or utilizing different types of milk. Additionally, it was noted that the lipid profile of cheese was altered by the use of vegetable oils such as soybean oil. Moreover, additional substances that might be utilized in the adulteration of cheeses include curd and flour. Future research on this topic is advised, as it appears that some food additives can be utilized to adulterate cheese. Occasionally, these additions decrease the nutritional value and create toxicity in food products. Mozzarella, Ricotta, hard, feta, butter, and Parmigiano Reggiano cheeses (animal; goat, caprine, and sheep, respectively) had the highest level of fraud.

2.2.3 Technical challenges

As already presented, the global market for cheese is projected to grow, and so does food fraud. Easy, reasonably priced and reliable detection methods are crucial to combat food fraud, and to ensure food safety. Several methods have been developed in recent years to detect fraud in cheese products. These are stable isotopes, silicon photonic immune sensor, image analysis, Iso Electro Focusing (IEF), liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS), nano flow RP LC- MS (RP-LC-MS), polymerase chain reaction (PCR), droplet digital PCR (ddPCR), Fourier transform near-infrared spectroscopy (FT-NIR), competitive ELISA, QPCR ASSAY, sensory analysis, electrophoresis

(SDS-PAGE), LC/electrospray ionization/MS (LC/ESI-MS), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) coupled with cluster analysis, and FTIR-ATR spectroscopy coupled with multivariate and NIR spectroscopy, as reviewed by Abedini et al. (2023).

However, cutting-edge techniques like machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI) are appealing subjects for fraud assessment. Artificial intelligence (AI) is highly capable of accurately assessing fraud. Among the AI-based techniques are media-based data analysis (text mining, network analysis). By carefully analyzing data and historical research, AI can forecast fraud and quality. Another cutting-edge method is deep learning, which involves carefully examining safety criteria using images from smartphones and satellites (Jahanbakhshi et al., 2021).

Traceability as a tool for ensuring cheese quality, safety and authenticity

Food industry health crises, such as the risk of disease transmission from animals to humans, have drawn attention to the importance of knowing where food comes from and the path it has taken to consumers' plate, i.e. traceability. Traceability is defined as "the ability to follow the movement of food through specific stages of production, processing, and distribution" (FAO, 2018). The Codex Alimentarius Commission has adopted the guideline: "*Principles for Traceability/Product Tracing as a Tool Within a Food Inspection and Certification System*" (CAC/CXG 60-2006).

The traceability system in the dairy sector implies that each animal intended for human consumption can be precisely identified from birth to transformation into a food product (origin, sex, breed, age, movements, and veterinary treatments).

Food traceability is defined as "the ability to trace, through all stages from primary production to distribution, the path of a food, animal feed, or substance intended to be incorporated or likely to be incorporated into a food or animal feed" (Tunisian Law No. 25 of February 26, 2019 relating to the health safety of foodstuffs and animal feed, JORT of March 22, 2019).

In Europe, the traceability of dairy products, including those from goats and sheep, is regulated by strict European Union (EU) standards. These standards aim to guarantee food safety, product quality and ensure transparency throughout the supply chain. It is important to note that specific regulations may vary between countries within the EU, but the entire system is designed to ensure full traceability of dairy products. Here are some key points of the dairy product traceability system in Europe:

- **Animal Identification:** Each animal must be uniquely identified, often using a microchip or ear tag. These identifiers allow the origin of dairy products to be traced back to the individual animal.
- **Registration of farms:** Farms that produce goat and sheep milk are required to register with the relevant authorities. These records include information about animals, breeding practices, etc.
- **Collection of production data:** Data relating to milk production, such as the quantity of milk produced per animal, is recorded. This helps establish a link between the final product and its origin.
- **Processing and Packaging:** Companies that process milk into dairy products, such as goat or sheep cheese, must also follow strict standards. Product batches must be clearly labeled, and information on the origin of the milk used must be recorded.

- **Labeling of finished products:** Finished dairy products, such as cheese, must be labeled in a way that allows their identification and traceability. This often includes information about the location of production, batch number, and other details.
- **Controls and inspections:** The competent authorities carry out regular checks to ensure that traceability standards are respected. This may include inspections of farms, processing facilities and points of sale.

Similarly, in Tunisia, animal traceability is mandatory: in regulatory terms, it is governed by the (i) Order of the Minister of Agriculture and the Minister of Health of May 31, 2012, establishing the list of animals concerned by traceability and their products, as well as the terms of their traceability and (ii) Order of the Minister of Agriculture and the Environment of December 9, 2011, establishing the list of animals concerned by identification: the list of animals concerned by identification includes cattle, sheep, goats, camelids, horses and rabbits. Animals are identified by the OEP services by ear tags including a unique and non-repeating number accompanying the animal throughout its life. The traceability of agri-food products is also mandatory for products subject to health approval such as cheeses (Karaa and Morana, 2008). According to Debbabi, Ben Ismail & Jmal (2023), the semi-industrial processing units from Béja region, that are also playing the role of collection centers, have set up a traceability system: they provide cans of milk to farmers on which they have affixed a breeder code, and thus know the origin of the milk used. A quality control of the milk is carried out upon receipt. Common analyzes are carried out: density, butter content and pH. More in-depth analyses are carried out using a lactoscan to analyze a small number of randomly chosen samples daily, in order to combat fraud and guarantee product quality. This information is recorded on sheets including the breeder codes. Subsequently, the units implemented an internal traceability system for monitoring their production (qualitative monitoring). In the event of non-compliance at the finished product level, an internal investigation is carried out to identify the cause of the problem. Semi-industrial units have also developed logistics traceability (locating the product in space and time). For distribution, they provide delivery sheets (product name, manufacturing date, number of product pieces, etc.) to the various points of sale. There are contracts between processors and traders, mostly verbal (82.9% of traders surveyed). In Béja, processors deliver to their own points of sale.

3.1 Traceability systems

Traceability systems for goat and sheep dairy products can use various digital technologies to track the journey of products throughout the supply chain. Digital traceability systems for dairy products are based on technologies and methods such as:

- **QR Codes and Barcodes:** Each product can be equipped with a unique QR code or barcode. Consumers can scan these codes with their smartphones to access detailed information about product origin, production date, breeding practices, and more.
- **RFID (Radio-Frequency Identification):** RFID tags can be attached to products, packaging or even animals. These tags contain digital information that can be read remotely using an RFID scanner, making it easier to track throughout the supply chain.

- **Mobile Applications:** Specific mobile applications can be developed to enable consumers to obtain real-time information on dairy products. These apps can also provide notifications about product recalls, special offers, etc.
- **Online platforms:** Online platforms can be set up to enable supply chain actors, such as producers, processors and distributors, to capture and track information about each batch of dairy products.
- **Blockchain:** Blockchain technology can be used to create a decentralized and secure ledger of all transactions and product movements throughout the supply chain. Each participant in the chain can have access to this register, which reinforces transparency and traceability.
- **IoT (Internet of Things) Sensors:** IoT sensors can be integrated into product packaging or directly into production equipment to monitor parameters such as temperature, humidity, etc. This data can be recorded digitally and contribute to traceability.
- **Supply Chain Management Systems:** Integrated supply chain management software can be used to track raw materials, production, distribution, and other key aspects of dairy product production.
- **Supply Chain Management (SCM) Systems:** SCM software often incorporates traceability features. These systems enable companies to efficiently manage their entire supply chain, from production to distribution.
- **Data Analytics:** Data analytics tools can be used to extract actionable insights from data collected throughout the supply chain. This can include predictive analytics, consumer trends, etc.
- **Cloud computing:** Storing data in the cloud makes it easier to access and share information throughout the supply chain. This allows different actors in the supply chain to access data collaboratively.

The main traceability tools used in MEDIFIT project for honey and cheese are barcode and QR Code are the most basic and widely-used digital traceability tools. Some Mediterranean products, including certain honeys and cheeses, have Geographical Indication (GI) Labels. Laboratory Testing allows the analysis of product composition, which can help to verify authenticity and detect adulteration.

The effectiveness of digital traceability systems highly depends on factors like regulations, standards, industry collaboration, and consumer awareness.

These measures aim to guarantee food safety, prevent fraud, and provide consumers with reliable information on the origin of the dairy products they purchase. Adoption of these technologies may vary by company and region, but the common goal is to improve the traceability, transparency and safety of goat and sheep dairy products.

3.2 Digital Tools to Improve Food Supply Chain Safety and Authenticity

Increasing the precision and effectiveness of food authenticity certification can be achieved through the digitalization of microbiological food safety risk assessment and quality indicators. Numerous digital tools are available to enhance food safety and preservation across the supply chain. These tools provide risk detection and prediction for food safety as well as the tracking, monitoring, and

tracing of food goods. Possas et al. (2022) have reviewed predictive microbiology software tools and resources launched mainly from 2016 to 2020. Sensors to track temperature, humidity, and other environmental factors that can affect hygiene are a few examples of digital tools for increased food chain protection. Blockchain technology also helps to trace the movement of food products throughout the supply chain, identifying potential risks to food sanitation and evaluating the efficacy of food security measures. In order to find patterns and trends that can point to hazards to food safety, a lot of data, such as that from sensor networks or food security inspections, must be analyzed. Artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies even assist in this process.

Electronic Product Code Information Service (EPCIS) standard is rapidly becoming the standard for traceability best practices (ISO/IEC 19987), enabling a more visible supply chain. Recently, sensor reports can be included in EPCIS. Food safety traceability system created by combining blockchain and EPCIS may better tackle the current food safety and authenticity problem. This combined approach may allow for the scalability of the entire system while supporting the tamper-proof nature of sensitive information (Lin et al., 2019).

MicroHibro is a web-based tool dedicated to enhancing food quality and safety. Developed by the PAID AGR-0170 (HIBRO) team at the University of Córdoba (Spain), it has received support from several regional, national, and international projects. The software is available at www.microhibro.com and free access after registration.

This tool aims at supporting food safety and quality in food industries, research, and official food control. Apart from food safety applications, MicroHibro is used as an educational resource, facilitating the training in fundamental concepts in both predictive microbiology and Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) domains (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Main page of Microhibro tool

Currently, MicroHibro comprises four modules that cover predictive microbiology models, shelf-life models, farm-to-fork models and sampling plans (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Four main modules of Microhibro

The prediction module includes predictive models describing microbial growth, inactivation, or transfer of foodborne pathogens and spoilage microorganisms. Models are stored in a dedicated database based on the MicroHibro and FSKX standard (Filter et al., 2022; González et al., 2019; Plaza-Rodríguez et al., 2018). Models can be selected through a navigation tree, a search window applying different filters such as model category, food, and parameters, or a decision system based on answers to specific questions. From the selected model, MicroHibro returns predicted kinetic parameters, such as the maximum growth or inactivation rate, latency time, maximum population density, and D-value, among others depending on the type of model. Predictions are also represented graphically, reflecting those changes in the model parameters (Figure 14). Models can be also challenged with data provided by the user, so as to validate MicroHibro models for specific user applications, related to particular food products or food processing conditions.

The shelf-life is a specific feature which allows users to validate product shelf-life based on sensory, physicochemical, and microbiological criteria. These attributes can be predicted with specific models included in the MicroHibro database. Attributes can be predicted jointly providing users with a comprehensive analysis of the effect of distinct shelf-life factors.

Figure 14 : Microhibro’s predictive module dashboard

The farm-to-table module is specifically dedicated to develop food chain models able to represent the effect, in combination, of different food processes or food stages. The module can be used to predict the dynamics of sensory, physicochemical and microbiological parameters (Figure 15). The construction of farm-to-table models is carried out with models contained in MicroHibro data base. Each food step is described by selecting a specific model and joining it to the previous one using a object-based system.

Figure 15 : From farm-to-table module dashboard in Microhibro

The sampling plans module provides users with a range of tools to create, assess, and enhance sampling plans, as well as formulate microbiological criteria for food. Practical examples are available to facilitate the development of sampling plans and microbiological criteria by introducing risk metrics such as Performance Objectives (PO) and Food Safety Objectives (FSO). Additionally, the application aids users to design customized sampling plans through a guided system.

In MEDIFIT, MicroHibro has adopted the EPCIS standard, based on FSKX scheme, enabling it to share models and predictions in an EPCIS repository. With this development, MicroHibro capabilities can be integrated in digital traceability systems, providing food stakeholders and food players with predictive tools to assess microbial food safety and prevent foodborne cases in real time and in a transparent and manner.

In addition, mobile apps facilitate the reporting of food safety concerns by enabling users to access secure information concerning food recalls and outbreaks of foodborne illness. Therefore, using digital tools can assist to increase the efficiency and efficacy of efforts related to food safety, which will eventually serve to safeguard customers and guarantee the security of the food supply.

3.3 The MEDIFIT digital solution

Food traceability and integrity in Mediterranean supply chains are supported by the Digital Platform for Food Integrity and Traceability of Relevant Mediterranean Supply Chains, or MEDIFIT, which makes use of cutting-edge analytical tools and methodologies. Its purpose is to give food safety experts up-to-date information and analysis so they can track food goods as they move through the supply chain and spot any problems with quality or safety. The MEDIFIT solution is based on novel not-target methods (NIR, Raman, RMN, etc.) in combination with the application of cutting-edge digital technology. Utilizing a blend of cutting-edge analytical methods, including blockchain technology, data mining, and machine learning, it examines food samples to determine their provenance and path through the supply chain. The Risk Assessment Modelling and Knowledge Integration Platform (RAKIP) Initiative aims at supporting researchers working on food safety and integrity. RAKIP Initiative has exemplified a strategy for future information exchange and integration

for the microbial risk assessment domain. In MEDIFIT, EPCIS was synergistically integrated along with FSKX (Food Safety Knowledge Exchange) by RAKIP and MicroHibro prediction tool. The benefit of MEDIFIT is its capacity to deliver accurate and timely traceability data, which can enhance the efficacy and efficiency of food safety initiatives. Additionally, it can assist in identifying any hazards to food safety and quality problems early in the supply chain, enabling the taking of corrective action in a more timely manner. In summary, MEDIFIT is a cutting-edge digital platform that might completely transform the management of food traceability and integrity in Mediterranean supply chains, hence enhancing the delivery of safe and high-quality food.

Therefore MEDIFIT solution will help to answer and address these challenges for honey and cheese sectors, and support new value chains by:

- **Addressing Authenticity & Counterfeiting**

It offers an authentic record of each product's journey. For sectors like honey and cheese where authenticity is paramount, this system ensures that every item can be traced back to its origin, combating counterfeits and adulterated products.

- **Sustainable Production & Sourcing**

MEDIFIT Solution captures data from the point of origin to ensure transparency. This transparency allows producers and consumers to verify sustainable and ethical sourcing of ingredients and materials. E.g., by ensuring that a certain cheese is produced from free-grazing animals or honey is harvested using eco-friendly methods. With the farm-to-table module of Microhibro, the software can contribute to optimize food processes through a microbiological perspective.

- **Quality Assurance**

MEDIFIT Solutions utilize cutting-edge analytical methods and EPCIS, as an electronic standard, improving food safety and quality assessment of mediterranean food products. MicroHibro, a prediction tool for microbial quality and safety, has been adapted, based on EPCIS and FSKX, to be integrated in traceability systems, providing predictions and data that can be traceability, accessible and usable along the food supply chain, by food consultants, food producers and food authorities. Introducing scientific tools for food integrity assessment into the traceability systems will improve transparency and reliability in the food chain. With the inclusion of sensorReports in EPCIS 2.0, stakeholders can monitor critical parameters like temperature or humidity in real-time. For temperature-sensitive products like certain cheeses or raw honey, this ensures quality and safety standards are met throughout the supply chain.

- **Streamlined Supply Chain**

MEDIFIT Solution offers real-time visibility into the movement and status of goods. This can lead to better inventory management, reduced wastage, and timely responses to supply chain disruptions. The sampling plans module of Microhibro can assist in creating and enhancing sampling plans, improving the efficiency of quality control processes in the supply chain. This contributes to a more streamlined and effective supply chain for cheese products.

- Consumer Trust & Engagement

MEDIFIT Solution enhances consumer trust through transparent data. The educational component of Microhibro can be used to outreach several food-related players, from farm to fork, providing proof of application of the efficiency of using innovative integrated food safety solutions. User-friendly tools, such as MicroHibro, can be leveraged to convey scientific results in an understandable and appealing manner, shared with different consumers and general populations, providing use cases within the food chains targeted by MEDIFIT, cheese product and honey.

By leveraging the transparent data offered by an EPCIS 2.0 repository, businesses can boost consumer trust. Additionally, they can create interactive platforms where consumers can verify product authenticity and learn about the product's journey, fostering brand loyalty.

- New Business Models & Opportunities

MEDIFIT Solution allows:

Data Monetization: Producers can offer access to their traceability data to third parties, such as researchers or marketers, opening new revenue streams. Microhibro's farm-to-table module can be used to assess different processes in the cheese supply chain. Producers can leverage this information to create new business models, such as premium product lines supported by Microhibro's prediction and models.

Collaborative Ventures: With a standardized system in place, businesses can easily collaborate, forming new partnerships or joint ventures. For example, a cheese producer might collaborate with a logistics company specializing in cold storage transport.

Premium Product Lines: Producers can launch premium product lines leveraging the transparency and assurance provided by MEDIFIT EPCIS 2.0, attracting a niche market willing to pay more for verified quality and authenticity.

Regulatory Compliance & Market Access

Robust traceability ensures that producers meet regulatory requirements, paving the way for easier access to international markets which have stringent traceability and quality norms.

- Informed Decision Making

MEDIFIT Solution provides comprehensive data for informed decision-making. Indeed, the comprehensive data collected can be analyzed to derive actionable insights. Producers can optimize their processes, reduce costs, and make informed decisions on production volumes, distribution channels, and marketing strategies. The different modules of Microhibro, including the prediction module and shelf-life module, can provide detailed information for decision-making in cheese production. Producers can optimize processes based on Microhibro's predictions and assessments.

In conclusion, the MEDIFIT solution is a cutting-edge digital platform that might completely transform the management of food traceability and integrity in Mediterranean supply chains, hence enhancing the delivery of safe and high-quality food.

Novel policy strategies, policy instruments, governance mechanisms and institutional changes

Novel policy strategies for promoting digital traceability should be based on:

- Geographical Indications (GIs): GIs enhance local economic development by promoting regional products and tourism.
- Traceability and Labeling: Enforcing clear labeling indicating origin, processing methods, additives, and other information.
- Sustainable Production
- Quality Standards and Testing
- Research and Development Support
- Funding research into improving food safety, traceability and quality, as well as digitalization.
- Supporting innovations in cheese production, safety, and packaging.
- Economic and Trade Policies
- Consumer Education

To promote digital traceability in the goat and sheep dairy food industry, policymakers can implement various policy instruments. These instruments are designed to create a regulatory environment that encourages the adoption of digital traceability technologies and practices. Several policy instruments can be employed to foster dairy food digital traceability:

Regulations and Legislation

- **Mandatory Digital Traceability Requirements:** Governments can establish laws requiring dairy producers, processors, and distributors to implement digital traceability systems. This may involve using technologies such as RFID, barcoding, or blockchain for tracking and recording relevant information.

- **Data Standards:** Implementing standardized data formats and protocols for digital traceability systems can ensure interoperability and consistency across the dairy supply chain.

Standards and Certification

- Digital Traceability Standards: Developing industry-wide digital traceability standards can help guide dairy businesses in implementing effective systems. These standards can cover data formats, interoperability, and security.
- Certification Programs: Establishing certification programs that verify compliance with digital traceability standards can provide assurance to consumers and facilitate trust in the dairy supply chain.

Financial Incentives

- Grants and Subsidies: Providing financial incentives, such as grants or subsidies, to dairy businesses for the adoption of digital traceability technologies can help offset implementation costs.
- Tax Credits: Offering tax credits for investments in digital traceability infrastructure can encourage dairy businesses to upgrade their systems.

Technology Support

- Research and Development Funding: Allocating funds for research and development projects focused on improving digital traceability technologies specific to the dairy industry can drive innovation
- Technology Adoption Programs: Implementing programs that assist dairy businesses in adopting and integrating digital traceability technologies, including providing training and technical support.

Capacity Building and Training

- Education Programs: Developing educational programs to raise awareness about the benefits of digital traceability and providing training for dairy industry stakeholders on how to implement and maintain these systems.
- Technical Assistance: Offering technical assistance to smaller dairy businesses to help them overcome barriers to adopting digital traceability technologies.

Monitoring and Enforcement

- Audits and Inspections: Regular audits and inspections by regulatory agencies to ensure that dairy businesses comply with digital traceability requirements. Non-compliance could result in penalties or other enforcement actions.
- Data Security Regulations: Implementing regulations that address data security and privacy concerns associated with digital traceability systems to protect sensitive information.

International Collaboration

- Harmonization of Standards: Collaborating with international organizations and other countries to harmonize digital traceability standards for dairy products can facilitate global trade and cooperation.
- International Data Exchange Agreements: Establishing agreements that enable the secure exchange of digital traceability data across borders while ensuring compliance with privacy and security standards.
- Implementing a combination of these policy instruments can create a comprehensive framework for promoting digital traceability in the dairy food industry, enhancing transparency, and ensuring the safety and quality of goat and sheep dairy products.

In order to better tackle the current food safety and authenticity problem, the food safety traceability system can combine blockchain and EPCIS (Lin et al., 2019). To foster transitions towards a new paradigm of digital food companies using EPCIS 2.0, several steps must be taken in a longer-term perspective:

Awareness and Education

- Raise awareness about the benefits and capabilities of EPCIS 2.0.
- Offer training and workshops to industry stakeholders on how to implement and leverage EPCIS 2.0 for supply chain visibility and efficiency.

Infrastructure Development

- Ensure the existence of robust IT infrastructure that supports the implementation and scaling of EPCIS 2.0.
- Promote the development of software platforms and applications tailored to EPCIS 2.0.

Collaboration and Standardization

- Foster collaboration between stakeholders – from farmers and manufacturers to retailers and consumers.
- Encourage industry-wide adoption of EPCIS 2.0 to ensure data consistency and interoperability.

Data Privacy and Security

- Implement robust data security measures to ensure the protection of data shared across the supply chain.
- Educate stakeholders about data privacy regulations and best practices.

Integration with Emerging Technologies

- Promote the integration of EPCIS 2.0 with other emerging technologies such as IoT, AI, and machine learning.
- Develop systems where EPCIS events can trigger machine learning models leading to advanced analytics and predictions.

Regulatory Support

- Engage with regulatory bodies to ensure that EPCIS 2.0's capabilities align with current and future regulations, especially in the food sector.
- Advocate for policies that support the digital transformation of the food industry using standards like EPCIS 2.0.

Feedback Mechanisms

- Establish systems to gather feedback from stakeholders on challenges and improvements related to EPCIS 2.0 implementation.
- Continuously refine and update the standard based on industry needs. (through GS1 EPCIS related work-requests)

Consumer Engagement

- Educate consumers about the benefits of EPCIS 2.0-driven transparency, such as improved product authenticity and traceability.
- Develop consumer-facing applications that leverage EPCIS 2.0 data, offering insights into product journey, authenticity, and other relevant information.

Economic Incentives

- Offer financial incentives or subsidies to companies, especially in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), to adopt and implement EPCIS 2.0.
- Recognize and reward early adopters and innovators in the domain.

Research and Development

- Foster R&D initiatives that aim to expand the capabilities of EPCIS 2.0 in the food sector.
- Continue Collaboration with academic institutions and research organizations to explore new applications and improvements.

Cultural Shift

- Encourage a culture of transparency, collaboration, and innovation within the food industry.
- Promote the values of ethical sourcing, sustainability, and consumer trust, all of which can be enhanced by EPCIS 2.0.

New value chains and business opportunities

In the rapidly evolving landscape of food traceability, specialized tools are being implemented in the honey and cheese industries. In the cheese sector, software solutions are poised to optimize milk source verification, aging and maturation monitoring, and supply chain logistics. Advanced analytics enable precise grading and classification, while compliance management ensures adherence to industry standards. Waste reduction and sustainability efforts are also gaining traction. Retail and distribution platforms are streamlining transactions and bolstering traceability across the cheese supply chain. These innovations signify a promising frontier, where technology meets the demand for authenticity, quality, and transparency in food production.

New business opportunities can facilitate exploitation of EPCIS protocols by third parties (e.g., through making results available under open licenses). The main objective is to exploit the results generated by the project by ensuring a smooth transfer to all potential beneficiaries (from civil society to the scientific community) and for tapping into the potential of “valorization” of project results (either commercially or scientifically) as far as it is possible. Market strategies may be oriented to activities of mainstreaming (successful transfer of project results to appropriate stakeholders and decision-makers) and multiplication (convincing other end-users to adopt or apply the outputs of the project). Target groups for exploitation activities are :

- i) Public authorities, whose will use the EPCIS protocol to monitor, verify and decide the acceptability of food batches according to international standards;
- ii) SME Suppliers, who are small producers having the need of improving traceability and authenticity of their products, through a cost-effective solution technology;
- iii) Large companies having different independent headquarters (cooperatives) needing an interconnexion between companies and a data sharing system; and
- iv) Logistic/supply chains, comprising both the physical flow of goods and the associated flow of information.

New value chains and business opportunities are:

- **Enhanced Traceability & Authenticity**

Premium Authentic Products: With improved traceability, producers can market their cheese and honey as authentic and genuine, fetching premium prices.

- **Data-Driven Insights**

By capturing and analyzing data throughout the production process, producers can identify inefficiencies and optimize production techniques.

- **Demand Forecasting**

Integration of EPCIS data with machine learning models can provide accurate demand forecasting, reducing wastage and ensuring timely production.

- **Consumer Engagement**

Interactive Labels

QR codes or NFC tags can be used on cheese and honey packaging.

When scanned, these can lead consumers to a platform showing the product's journey, validated by EPCIS 2.0 data.

- **Loyalty Programs**

Engage consumers by offering rewards for purchasing authenticated products, driving repeat sales.

- **Supply Chain Optimization**

Real-time visibility into product movement can help in better inventory management, reducing holding costs and wastage.

With better visibility into the supply chain, businesses can implement dynamic pricing strategies based on demand and supply.

- **Collaborative Opportunities**

Cheese and honey producers can collaborate with tech providers to create integrated solutions, combining IoT sensors and EPCIS 2.0 standards.

Third-party agencies can offer certification services for cheese and honey producers, verifying and authenticating their traceability practices based on EPCIS 2.0 data.

- **Sustainable Practices**

Efficient tracking can lead to reduced wastage in the supply chain.

Eco Branding: With transparent practices, producers can position their products as sustainably produced, appealing to eco-conscious consumers.

- **Marketplace & Platforms**

Specialized Online Marketplaces: Platforms dedicated to authenticated cheese and honey products, ensuring consumers get genuine products.

B2B Platforms: Platforms where producers can showcase their traceability practices to attract bulk buyers or retailers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the development of the sheep and goat dairy value chain offers opportunities for economic growth and job creation, while contributing to the preservation of local agri-food traditions. Demand for quality dairy products, such as sheep and goat's milk cheese, is increasing, particularly due to their reputation as healthy and traditional products. Consumers are increasingly looking for alternatives to traditional dairy products, which opens up opportunities for the sheep and goat dairy industry. However, value chain development requires strategic planning, investments and collaboration between value chain players and governments to overcome region-specific challenges. The Tunisian dairy sheep and goat sector must meet challenges linked to the environment, resources, technology, quality and marketing to ensure its sustainability and competitiveness on the market. These challenges are actually interconnected and can vary depending on factors such as farm size, agricultural policies, available natural resources and socio-economic dynamics. Collaboration between governments, research institutions, agricultural professional organizations and breeders is essential to address these challenges and strengthen the sustainability and resilience of the sheep and goat dairy sector. This could include training programs, rural development measures, incentives for innovation, investments in infrastructure and digitalization, and the establishment of specific support policies for the sheep and goat dairy sector.

The digitalization which is at the heart of the EU PRIMA MEDIFIT project (2020-2023) offers great potential to improve the sheep and goat dairy sector in the Mediterranean basin by strengthening efficiency, sustainability and competitiveness. Digital technology now constitutes a lever for development. In this context, the use of technology and digital digitization makes it possible to accelerate agricultural production, and to improve certain more specific aspects of the work of breeders such as herd monitoring: traceability, optimization of feeding, genetics, the effectiveness of treatments, etc. It also makes it possible to facilitate the administrative management of farms (payroll, invoicing, accounting, etc.). On the other hand, digital technologies offer the possibility of accessing information on best breeding practices, animal health and herd management. This can be particularly beneficial for small breeders who need to strengthen their skills. Consequently, it constitutes for the breeder a means of managing his farm more carefully and making informed decisions. Digitalization can also help reduce the environmental footprint of the sheep and goat dairy industry by optimizing the use of resources such as water, energy and feed. Additionally, it can make it easier to track sustainable practices, which can be an asset in environmentally conscious markets.

However digitalization requires careful planning and collaboration between industry players to take full advantage of it. In addition to improving productivity and quality, improving livestock management and better access to markets, digitalization can support the development of new products and services, like in the EU PRIMA MEDIFIT project. Indeed, the data collected through digitalization can be used to develop new sheep and goat dairy products, meeting the changing needs of consumers, such as organic products or value-added products. Digitalization can also contribute to optimizing the supply chain. Digital traceability such as the digital solution developed by the EU PRIMA MEDIFIT project can be implemented to follow the entire production process, from farm to table. The MEDIFIT solution is based on the use of the latest analytical and software

technologies. By combining for instance, blockchain and EPCIS 2.0, and the inclusion of sensor reports in EPCIS 2.0, this solution helps ensure the quality and authenticity of sheep and goat dairy products, which can enhance consumer confidence. In MEDIFIT, MicroHibro capabilities were developed in order to be integrated in digital traceability systems, providing food stakeholders and food players with predictive tools to assess microbial food safety and prevent foodborne cases in real time and in a transparent manner. However, the implementation of this digitalization requires investments in terms of technology, training and infrastructure.

Finally, to effectively tackle the challenges faced by the Mediterranean region, it will be interesting to promote the adoption of the MEDIFIT integrated approach. This will require the EU to engage in policy dialogues centered on research and innovation. In fact, the establishment of a significant stride towards the formation of a union among Southern neighborhood countries is underway and the development of a shared research and innovation agenda within the Mediterranean region is a key focus of the Knowledge and Innovation Area (CKIS).

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